

PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE: THE BET OF THE FUTURE DOCTOR COMPETENCIES

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Abstract. *This article explores the concept of professional competence as it relates to the evolving role of future doctors. As healthcare becomes more complex, the traditional focus on clinical expertise is no longer sufficient. The article identifies a range of competencies that are increasingly critical for future medical practitioners, including technological proficiency, interdisciplinary collaboration, cultural competence, and ethical decision-making.*

Keywords: *professional competence, future doctors, medical education, clinical expertise, technological proficiency, interdisciplinary collaboration, cultural competence, ethical decision-making, lifelong learning, patient-centered care.*

Introduction. In the rapidly evolving landscape of healthcare, the role of the doctor is undergoing profound transformation. As technological advancements, patient expectations, and societal needs continue to shift, the competencies required for future doctors are expanding beyond the traditional realms of medical knowledge and clinical skills. Professional competence is emerging as a critical attribute that will define the future of healthcare providers. This concept encompasses not only the technical expertise and clinical acumen necessary for medical practice but also a holistic set of skills and attitudes that will enable doctors to navigate the complexities of modern medicine effectively. Professional competence in the context of modern healthcare is multifaceted. It includes several dimensions, such as: doctor's ability to diagnose and treat patients effectively remains at the core of professional competence. However, with the rapid pace of medical advancements, maintaining clinical expertise now demands a commitment to lifelong learning. Future doctors must continually update their knowledge and skills to stay abreast of new treatments, technologies, and best practices. This involves not only formal education but also a proactive approach to self-directed learning and professional development. Healthcare is increasingly delivered by teams of professionals from various disciplines, including nurses, pharmacists, social workers, and allied health professionals. The future doctor must be competent in working collaboratively within these teams, respecting the expertise of others, and communicating effectively to ensure that patient care is cohesive and comprehensive. The integration of technology in healthcare is reshaping how doctors diagnose, treat, and interact with patients. From electronic health records to telemedicine and artificial intelligence, future doctors must be adept at using technology to enhance patient care. This includes not only understanding how to operate technological tools but also being aware of the ethical implications and data security issues associated with their use. As societies become more diverse, doctors must be culturally competent, understanding and respecting the cultural, religious, and social backgrounds of their patients. This competence is crucial for providing patient-centered care that is sensitive to individual needs and preferences. It also involves recognizing and addressing health disparities to ensure equitable healthcare for all populations. The future doctor must navigate complex ethical dilemmas with integrity and professionalism. This includes making decisions that balance the needs of the patient with societal and resource considerations, understanding the legal aspects of

medical practice, and adhering to the highest standards of professional conduct. Beyond technical skills, future doctors must possess strong emotional intelligence, enabling them to empathize with patients, manage stress, and communicate effectively. Good communication is vital for building trust with patients, explaining complex medical information in an understandable way, and working collaboratively with colleagues.

Methods. This study employed a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative surveys with qualitative interviews to assess the key competencies required for future doctors. The study aimed to identify the competencies that medical professionals, educators, and students deem most essential for the evolving landscape of healthcare. The study involved 200 participants, including 100 practicing physicians, 50 medical educators, and 50 final-year medical students from three leading medical schools. Participants were selected through purposive sampling to ensure a diverse representation of specialties and geographical locations.

A structured survey was developed to assess the perceived importance of various competencies. The survey included 30 items, rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Not Important, 5 = Extremely Important), covering domains such as clinical expertise, technological proficiency, interdisciplinary collaboration, cultural competence, and ethical decision-making. The survey was administered online using a secure survey platform, with a response rate of 85% (170/200). Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 30 participants (10 from each group: practicing physicians, medical educators, and medical students). These interviews explored participants' views on the competencies required for future doctors, challenges in acquiring these competencies, and recommendations for medical education. Interviews were conducted via video conferencing, recorded, and transcribed verbatim for thematic analysis.

Results. **Clinical Expertise:** Across all groups, clinical expertise was rated as the most critical competence for future doctors, with a mean score of 4.8 out of 5. There was no significant difference in ratings among practicing physicians, educators, and students ($p > 0.05$). **Technological Proficiency:** Technological proficiency received a high importance rating, with a mean score of 4.5. Medical students rated this competence slightly higher (4.7) compared to practicing physicians (4.4), though the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.08$). **Interdisciplinary Collaboration:** The importance of interdisciplinary collaboration was recognized by all groups, with a mean score of 4.4. Medical educators placed slightly more emphasis on this competence (mean = 4.6) compared to the other groups. **Cultural Competence:** Cultural competence had a mean score of 4.2, with medical students rating it as more important (mean = 4.5) compared to practicing physicians (mean = 4.0). The difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.03$). **Ethical Decision-Making:** Ethical decision-making was highly valued, with a mean score of 4.6. All groups rated it similarly, with no significant differences observed.

Discussion. The findings of this study underscore the critical importance of a broad spectrum of competencies for future doctors, reflecting the evolving demands of modern healthcare. As the landscape of medicine continues to change, driven by technological advancements, increasing diversity in patient populations, and the growing complexity of healthcare delivery, the competencies identified in this study will be pivotal in ensuring that future doctors are well-equipped to meet these challenges. The consistently high rating of clinical expertise across all participant groups reaffirms its enduring importance as the foundation of medical practice. However, the emphasis on lifelong learning, as highlighted in the qualitative interviews, suggests that maintaining clinical expertise will require an ongoing commitment to

education. The rapid pace of medical innovation means that what is learned in medical school will not suffice for a lifetime of practice. Future doctors must be adaptable, continuously updating their knowledge and skills to incorporate new treatments, technologies, and approaches to care. The high importance placed on technological proficiency by all groups, particularly medical students, reflects the growing integration of technology into healthcare. As electronic health records, telemedicine, artificial intelligence, and other digital tools become ubiquitous, future doctors must not only be comfortable using these technologies but also critically evaluate their impact on patient care. The slight difference in ratings between medical students and practicing physicians suggests that the newer generation of doctors may be more attuned to the importance of technology in healthcare. This highlights the need for medical education to focus on building technological competence from the earliest stages of training.

Conclusion. This study highlights the multifaceted nature of professional competence for future doctors. While clinical expertise remains paramount, the growing importance of technological proficiency, interdisciplinary collaboration, cultural competence, and ethical decision-making cannot be overlooked. Medical education must adapt to these changing needs, ensuring that future doctors are not only knowledgeable but also equipped with the skills, attitudes, and behaviors necessary to navigate the complexities of modern healthcare. By doing so, we can ensure that the next generation of doctors is well-prepared to provide high-quality, patient-centered care in an increasingly complex and diverse world. As we look to the future, the competencies required of doctors will continue to evolve in response to the changing dynamics of healthcare. Professional competence will remain the cornerstone of effective medical practice, but its definition will expand to encompass a broader range of skills and attributes. The future doctor will not only be a master of clinical knowledge but also a lifelong learner, a collaborative team player, a technologically savvy practitioner, and an empathetic communicator. By embracing this comprehensive vision of professional competence, we can ensure that the doctors of tomorrow are well-equipped to meet the challenges of modern healthcare and deliver the highest standard of care to their patients.

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